

identified as resorcinol (6) as it responded to ferric chloride, Tollen's reagent and Fehling's solution tests, and further confirmed by m.p. and m.m.p.

The other dyes (4a-h) were prepared and analysed similarly as mentioned in the case of 4b.

2-p-Toluyyl-3-nitrobenzoic acid was prepared⁷ using Friedel-Crafts reaction between toluene and nitrophthalic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. p-Toluyylresorcinol/nitrophthalic acid (5b) and other dyes of the series (5a-h) were prepared similarly as dyes 4a-h.

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Studies on Infrared Spectra of some Indenoisocoumarins

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INDENO[2,1-c]isocoumarins are the derivatives of isocoumarins where the 3,4-position is fused with an indeno ring. The purpose of the present work is to determine the infrared absorption spectra of 5,8-dimethoxyindeno[2':3'-3:4]isocoumarin, 5,7-dimethoxyindeno[2':3'-3:4]isocoumarin, 5,7-dimethoxyindeno[2':3'-3:4]isocoumarin, 7-methoxyindeno[2':3'-3:4]isocoumarin, 6,7 dimethoxyindeno[2':3'-3:4]isocoumarin, 5,8,5',6'-tetramethoxyindeno[2':3'-3:4]isocoumarin, 5,7,5',6'-tetramethoxyindeno[2':3'-3:4]isocoumarin, 7,5',6'-trimethoxyindeno[2':3'-3:4]isocoumarin and 6,7,5',6'-tetramethoxyindeno[2':3'-3:4]isocoumarin have been studied with reference to the frequency of C=O and -O-C= groups of the pyran ring. There was appreciable change due to variation of methoxy group at different positions in benzene ring.

No ir data appear to have been reported for -O-C= group on the compounds studied in the present work.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of the indeno[2,1-c]isocoumarins studied shows that these have marked similarity except in some cases. In all the indeno[2,1-c]isocoumarins, the ir absorption of C=O of lactone groups is found in the normal range 1 705-1 725 cm⁻¹ except 1b and 1d. 1b and 1d have two values of ir absorption, i.e. 1 700 1 710 and 1 710, 1 700 cm⁻¹. 1e reveals two values of ir absorptions 1 705, 1 720 cm⁻¹ in the normal range 1 705-1 725 cm⁻¹. In all the indenoisocoumarins the ir absorption of -O-C= group is found in the normal range (1 100-1 300 cm⁻¹).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Molecular formula	M.p.* °C	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{-O-C=}$
1a	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	161-62 ^a	1 720	1 110
1b	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	145-46 ^b	1 700, 1 710	1 100
1c	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₃	158-59 ^b	1 710	1 108
1d	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	202-05 ^b	1 700, 1 710	1 110
1e	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	123d ^b	1 705, 1 720	1 125
1f	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	160-61 ^c	1 715	1 120
1g	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	124-26 ^c	1 708	1 112
1h	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	169-71 ^c	1 710	1 115

*Crystallised from : ^aEtOH-EtOAc, ^bEtOH, ^cEtOAc.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer. The indenoisocoumarins were prepared¹ by the following procedure. Substituted-benzoic acids on treatment with 2-bromoindan-1-one and 2-bromo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one separately in ethanolic NaOH (5%) at pH 6.5 furnished the corresponding 1-oxo-2-indanyl benzoates, which on cyclodehydration in 90% sulphuric acid² or PPA yielded the respective indeno[2,1-c]isocoumarins (1a-h). The compound were purified by repeated fractional crystallisation showing melting point within a range of 1-2°.

- 1a; R¹-OMe; R-R²-R³-R⁴-R⁵-H
- 1b; R-R²-OMe; R¹-R³-R⁴-R⁵-H
- 1c; R¹-R²-OMe; R-R³-R⁴-R⁵-H
- 1d; R¹-R²-OMe; R-R³-R⁴-R⁵-H
- 1e; R¹-R⁴-OMe; R-R²-R³-H
- 1f; R-R²-R⁴-R⁵-OMe; R¹-R³-H
- 1g; R¹-R²-R⁴-R⁵-OMe; R-R³-H
- 1h; R¹-R²-R⁴-R⁵-OMe; R-R³-H

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**Addition-Elimination Reactions of
4- and 6-Chloroindolin-2,3-diones with
Aromatic Amines**

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IN continuation of our work¹ on addition-elimination reactions of 4- and 6-chloroindolin-2,3-diones (1a, b), we report herein the nucleophilic addition-elimination reactions of 1a and b with aromatic amines.

Nucleophilic attack of anilines on 4- and 6-chloroindolin-2,3-diones (1a, b) underwent smoothly leading to 4a and b in excellent yields. 1a and 1b were treated with dimethyl sulphate and ethanolic KOH to get the corresponding 1-methyl analogs which were again treated with anilines leading to 3a and 3b respectively. Further, Mannich condensation on 4a and 4b resulted in the formation of 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-4/6-chloro-3-

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{KOH}-\text{EtOH}$, (ii) $\text{R.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2$ (p), (iii) morpholine/piperidine/ HCHO .

(phenylimino)-2-indolinones (5a and 5b), which provided additional evidence for the structures of 4a and 4b (Scheme 1). All the compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

Mass spectrum of compound 6 showing characteristic chlorine profile was in conformity with the assigned structure (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

4-Chloro-1-methyl-3-(arylimino)-2-indolinones (3a) 4-Chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione (0.005 mol) was refluxed with *p*-chloroaniline (0.005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop) on a water-bath for 3-4 h. The orange crystals separated on cooling were dried and recrystallised from chloroform (Table 1).

6-Chloro-1-methyl-3-(arylimino)-2-indolinones (3b): The compounds were prepared by condensing 6-chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione (0.005 mol) with *p*-chloroaniline (0.005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop) on a water-bath for 3-4 h. The crystals that separated on cooling were filtered, dried and recrystallised from chloroform (Table 1).

4-Chloro-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (4a): A mixture of 4-chloroisatin (1.81 g, 0.01 mol) and substituted-aniline (0.01 mol) in methanol (15 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop) was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid product was washed with methanol.